

THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF SODIUM AND POTASSIUM NITRITES.
PART II. ACTION OF NITRIC OXIDE, OXYGEN AND NITROGEN
PEROXIDE ON THE FUSED NITRITES

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It is found that (i) nitrogen is produced by the action of nitric oxide on the fused nitrites; (ii) nitrogen peroxide in becoming reduced to nitrogen passes through the stage of nitric oxide; (iii) the nitrogen peroxide formed in the initial reversible stage by the dissociation of the nitrites reacts simultaneously with the produced alkali oxide and the nitrite in the residue, and (iv) the decomposition of alkali nitrites appears to be a case of homogeneous reactions proceeding to a very considerable extent, only in the molten mass. The mechanism of the reactions is discussed and formulated.

In Part I of this work it has been shown that sodium and potassium nitrite undergo decomposition in the initial stage as

and evidence has been obtained tending to explain the disappearance of nitrogen peroxide and appearance of nitrogen in the gas and nitrate in the residue. In this part further light is thrown on these and on the nature of the decomposition, more especially, on the mode of production of nitrogen.

The action of nitric oxide and nitrogen peroxide on sodium and potassium nitrite has been studied by Oswald (*Ann.Chim.*, 1914, 9, 32) who found that (i) nitric oxide did not act upon the nitrites till the latter decomposed and (ii) nitrogen peroxide reacted with them to produce both nitric oxide and nitrogen. He deduced that nitrogen was produced from nitrogen peroxide in a single step as :

On the other hand, Mehta (M.Sc., thesis abstract, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1941, 135) who studied the action of nitric oxide and nitrogen peroxide on potassium and silver nitrites, states that (i) nitrogen peroxide, produced from the nitrites in the initial stage, reacts with both the alkali oxide simultaneously produced and with the undecomposed nitrite producing nitric oxide in the latter case : evidence for this has already been adduced in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 173); (ii) nitrogen is produced by the action of nitric oxide on the nitrite in the reacting mass.

In this paper the results of streaming at a steady rate, measured volumes of nitric oxide and oxygen are described. Oxygen has been used in place of nitrogen peroxide since the latter cannot be conveniently measured and the results have been confirmed by using pure nitrogen peroxide itself. Experiments have also been described to throw light on the particular part played by the alkali oxide (in the residue) in the reactions and on the general nature of the reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Sodium and potassium nitrites were the same as those used in Part I. *Nitric oxide.*—Nitric oxide was prepared from FeSO_4 , H_2SO_4 , and KNO_3 . It was

first collected in an inverted bottle over air-free water and then carefully transferred, after drying over a long layer of P_2O_5 , to the evacuated reservoir with the help of a manometer. The gas was tested for purity; three samples gave the same results: e.g., 53.58 c.c. left 1.27 c.c. unabsorbed in alkaline Na_2SO_3 followed by acidified $FeSO_4$. The results in Table I are corrected for this impurity.

Oxygen.—Oxygen was prepared by heating $KClO_3 + MnO_2$ kept in a tube sealed on to the 4th way of the 4-way tap, T, in the apparatus (*vide fig.* Part I) previously evacuated and tested for leaks. The first few litres were pumped off and the subsequent lot collected for the experiments. On absorption in alkaline pyrogallol a very tiny bubble was left unabsorbed from about 25-30 c.c. of the gas.

Nitrogen peroxide.—Nitrogen peroxide was prepared by heating finely powdered $Pb(NO_3)_2$. The gases generated on heating were led into a U-tube immersed in a freezing mixture of ice and $CaCl_2$. When sufficient amount of the solid (dirty greenish) was collected, heating was discontinued, the solid allowed to liquefy and evaporate freely if necessary under partial vacuum. The liquid became colourless in course of time which was then again frozen to white mass and the gas transferred to the evacuated and tested reservoir by means of the apparatus shown in Fig. 1. Samples of the gas were absorbed in KOH in the apparatus (*vide fig.* Part I) and the KOH, analysed for nitrite and nitrate, gave equivalent amounts of the two.

FIG. 1

Procedure.—The apparatus used and the method of work were the same as described in Part I. The measuring burette was dispensed with in experiments with nitrogen peroxide. The recorded volumes are all at N.T.P. For the same reason as stated in Part I, results of solid residue analysis in Tables I, II, and III are approximate.

The results of experiments with nitric oxide are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Nitric oxide as the streaming gas

Substance.	Temp.	Total passed.	Gas obtained.	Compn. of gas			Residue (g.)		
				N_2O_2 (in K)	NO.	N_2 .	NO_2 .	NO .	O.
$NaNO_2$	380°	53.58 c.c.	55.77 c.c.	2.07	0	0.0	0.00	0.9800	0.0044
KNO_2	410	53.50	56.68	2.47	(apparently)	0.93	0.01075	0.9575	0.0165
KNO_2	460	59.19	62.87	3.30		1.26	0.01775	0.9360	0.0262

These results show that (i) nitrogen trioxide alone, unmixed with nitric oxide or nitrogen, in the gas and nitrate in the residue, is produced with sodium nitrite even at 380°. This is in line with the corresponding result with nitrogen as streaming gas (Part I); (ii) with potassium nitrite, on the other hand, all the three gases, viz., nitric oxide, nitrogen peroxide and nitrogen and also nitrate, are produced, their quantities increasing with temperature; (iii) the volume of nitrogen is greater than what corresponds to reduction in the volume of nitric oxide passed: this shows that the nitrogen was not all produced merely by the reduction of the streamed nitric oxide, i.e., some of it was necessarily produced from the decomposing nitrite.

If the results in this table are compared with the results in Table I (Part I) it can be inferred that the decomposition of the fused nitrites is retarded by the presence of nitric oxide in the system. This fact lends support to the reversible nature of the initial stage in the decomposition.

TABLE II

Oxygen as the streaming gas

Substance.	Temp.	Total passed.	Gas obtained.	O ₂ used up.	Gas produced (c.c.)	Compn. of gas			Residue (g.)		
						NO ₂ (in K)	NO.	N ₂ .	NO ₁ '.	NO ₂ '.	O ^o .
NaNO ₂	330°	53.67	51.5	3.7	11.26	9.8	0.0	1.46	0.0167	0.9570	0.0133
NaNO ₂	380	54.7	53.5	2.6	12.36	10.98	0.0	1.38	0.0165	0.9550	0.0143
KNO ₂	410	53.19	52.28	1.9	16.57	15.7	0.0	0.87	0.2000	0.9380	0.0283
KNO ₂	460	55.03	52.23	5.5	22.87	20.1	0.0	2.77	0.0490	0.9040	0.0303

The results of experiments on the streaming of oxygen are given in Table II. These results show that (i) the quantity of nitric oxide decomposed is comparatively high than in corresponding experiments with nitrogen or nitric oxide; the quantities of oxide and nitrate in the residue are comparatively large showing that the formation of these goes hand-in-hand with the decomposition; (ii) the amounts of nitrogen formed in these experiments, as compared with those formed in experiments with nitric oxide, (and also with nitrogen, Part I), are greater and it is very interesting to observe that the amounts of nitrogen formed appear to be related to the amounts of oxygen used up* and to the amounts of nitrate formed. It would thus appear that nitrate production and nitrogen production are related to the reactions consuming oxygen; (iii) more nitrate is produced in experiments with KNO₂ than with NaNO₂ showing that the former reacted in preference to the latter with the oxides of nitrogen; (iv) the amounts of nitrogen peroxide produced in the alkali are fairly large thus showing that a large quantity of nitric oxide is produced in these experiments.

* Oxygen used up (column 5, Table II) is found by subtracting the volume of nitrogen from the gas obtained and subtracting the result from the total oxygen passed.

The production of large quantities of nitrogen peroxide and the consumption of oxygen could be explained on the supposition that nitrogen peroxide is becoming reduced to nitrogen only in stages through the intermediate production of nitric oxide and *not* directly in one stage. The nitric oxide, produced in the decomposition (or, dissociation) takes up oxygen and forms nitrogen peroxide; the latter reacts with the nitrite and becomes reduced to nitric oxide; the reformed nitric oxide again takes up oxygen to form nitrogen peroxide and so on, the reactions consume oxygen and form nitrate. The simultaneous increase in nitrogen production receives explanation on the greater frequency of contacts of nitric oxide with the nitrite.

The results of experiments with nitrogen peroxide as streaming gas are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Nitrogen peroxide as the streaming gas

Substance.	Temp.	Total gas obtained.	KNO ₃ in alkali (K)	KNO ₂ in alkali	Compn. of gas			Residus	
					N ₂ O ₃ (absorbed in K)	NO	N ₂	NO ₃ '	NO ₂ '
NaNO ₂	330°	34.66 c.c.	0.1810 g.	0.0600 g.	6.25	28.25	0.16	0.0154	0.9876
NaNO ₂	380	36.57	0.202	0.0530	10.5	25.25	0.82	0.0338	0.9725
KNO ₂	410	34.34	0.1850	0.0553	8.2	24.7	1.44	0.0260	0.9780
KNO ₂	460	42.66	0.2314	0.0646	11.34	28.5	2.82	0.0570	0.9572

It will be seen that these results are quite comparable with those in Table II. They receive explanation also on similar lines. It is significant that the amount of nitrogen produced in experiments with KNO₂ and oxygen or nitrogen peroxide are quite comparable though this is not the case with NaNO₂. Ostwald (*loc. cit.*) found that nitric oxide did not act upon the nitrites till the latter decomposed while nitrogen peroxide did. If therefore nitrogen production was directly obtained by the reduction of nitrogen peroxide with the nitrite, comparable production of nitrogen should be observed in all these experiments. The results thus indirectly conform to the view already deduced from the experimental results of Table II and inferred from the results of experiments with MgO (Part I) that the nitrogen production does not result from nitrogen peroxide in one step. On the other hand, if the production of nitrogen depended upon the reduction of nitric oxide, then, since nitric oxide reacts with the nitrite only at higher temperatures, its production in the case of potassium nitrite and lack of production in the case of sodium nitrite find ready explanation.

The results may now be recapitulated with advantage. The facts recorded in Part I, substantiated by the additional evidence adduced in this part, show convincingly that the initial stage in the decomposition is the dissociation of the nitrites as

nitrogen and nitrate being produced in a subsequent stage. The facts that (i) nitrogen is produced in experiments with nitric oxide—a gas which acts on the nitrites only at higher temperatures; (ii) very large excess of nitrogen is not produced in experiments with oxygen or nitrogen peroxide which (latter) is known to act as oxidizing agent at much lower temperatures than does nitric oxide, show that nitrogen is produced by the reduction of nitric oxide. The evidence recorded in Part I (*e.g.* experiments with MgO) substantiates the same view. Thus, nitrogen is produced by the action of nitric oxide on the fused nitrites, as

Oza and Shah (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 11, 56) found that (i) gaseous products of the decomposition contained, in the initial stages, a very large proportion of nitric oxide and (ii) in none of the experiments was nitric oxide obtained unmixed with nitrogen. In view of (a) the now established nature of the primary stage in the decomposition (1), (b) great vigour of the reaction when the nitrites, mixed with MgO, undergo fusion and (c) the fact that the gaseous products in (b) consist of almost pure nitric oxide, the observation (i) of Oza and Shah receives explanation on the well known behaviour of nitrogen peroxide to oxides of alkali metals, as,

Such a behaviour, if quantitative, would consume half the alkali oxide and all nitrogen peroxide produced in (1) and the residue will still continue to indicate free alkali and will show the presence of nitrate while the gaseous products will contain only nitric oxide. Since, however, nitric oxide unmixed with nitrogen, has never been isolated, it would appear that the reactions (3) and (2) proceed hand-in-hand. Experimental facts (Table III) indicate that nitrogen peroxide can react with potassium nitrite also as

and it is therefore not unlikely that this reaction, too, may be proceeding side by side with reactions (2) and (3). The available experimental evidence as to the quantitative nature of the gaseous products and the residue could be explained both on reactions (2) and (3) or on (2), (3) and (4) following the primary stage (1).

A close observation into the above equations (1), (2), (3) and (4), can enable us to decide what actually happens. For, while there are two nitrogen peroxide consuming reactions (3 and 4) there is only one reaction (eqn. 1) producing and only one (3) consuming, the alkali oxide. Hence if the nitrogen peroxide reacted quantitatively, only with the alkali oxide according to (3), the amount of the oxide left in the residue should be given by the equation :

Thus, an exact determination of the amount of the alkali oxide in the residue at different stages in the decomposition can enable us to decide whether the nitrogen peroxide reacts in part also as in (4) or it reacts merely as in (3).

Four experiments were therefore performed on heating weighed quantities of pure NaNO_2 under different conditions at 380° , in a vacuum. Since glass is attacked by the alkali oxide, the nitrite was kept on a platinum surface. The platinum crucible, containing the substance, was enclosed in a glass tube heated in an electric furnace. The apparatus consisted of a glass tube passing through an internal seal to a flask containing some moist KOH and through the latter to the Sprengel pump. In the first experiment, a certain quantity of NaNO_2 was heated in a closed system till a certain quantity of gas was produced; in the second, the same quantity of NaNO_2 was mixed with its 25% NaNO_3 and heated in the same way: this was done to ascertain if the nitrate did decompose at this temperature and the results showed that it did; in the third, twice (that used in the first) the weight of pure NaNO_2 was heated under the same conditions as in the first with a view to finding the effect of mass and in the fourth experiment, the same weight (as that in the third) was heated with the pump working continuously so that the products of the reaction were not allowed to accumulate in the system and the surface reaction between the gas and the decomposing substance (also the solid products of the decomposition) was prevented. The results of these experiments are set out in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Experiments in the decomposition, at 380° , of NaNO_2 under different conditions

Wt. of substance (g.)	Time in hrs.	Total gas (c.c.)	Compn. of gas			Compn. of gas %		
			N_2O_2	NO	N_2	N_2O_2	NO	N_2
0.5000	55	14.82	0.4	5.7	8.7	2.7	38.4	58.8
0.5000 + 0.1250 NaNO_3	65	12.82	0.36	3.9	8.5	2.8	30.5	66.7
1.000	25	17.20	0.47	4.4	12.3	3.0	25.5	71.5
1.000	10	17.12	1.12	6.6	9.4	6.5	38.7	54.8

Residue in g.			Na_2O (Calc.)	Na_2O Ratio: Calc: Obs.	NaNO_3 formed per c.c. of N_2
NaNO_2	NaNO_2	Na_2O			
0.1085	0.3380	0.0331	0.0486	0.68	0.0124
0.2207	0.3612	0.0300	0.0416	0.72	0.0112
0.1500	0.7935	0.0450	0.0619	0.72	0.0121
0.1156	0.8210	0.0381	0.0537	0.71	0.0123

These results show that (i) a definite amount of nitrate is always produced per c.c. of nitrogen formed confirming the observation that nitrate and nitrogen-producing reactions go hand-in-hand; (ii) the oxide (Na_2O) actually found is less than what would be expected according to (5); (iii) the ratio, oxide (Na_2O) found to that formed according to (5), tends to remain constant during the reactions. This shows that all the nitrite used up does not decompose as in (1), but a definite fraction, indicated by the constancy of the ratio (iii), is used up as in (4). The above fact shows also that decomposition under study is a case of reactions proceeding in a homogeneous system. Hence, though the possibility of the

reactions (4) and (3) occurring at the gas-liquid (molten nitrite) interface is not precluded, the conditions prevailing in the system do not permit of escape of much nitrogen peroxide into the gas phase for reaction (4) to occur at the gas-liquid interface while the reaction (2), though it does occur at the interface, the extent of the reaction thus occurring must be very small since nitric oxide is much less reactive to nitrite than is nitrogen peroxide so that the ratio, nitrate : nitrogen, is not much affected by this heterogeneous reaction. In experiment 4, both nitrogen and nitric oxide are produced in amounts different from those in experiment 3 but it must be remembered that the effect of time is to produce more nitrogen (Oza and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

CONCLUSION

The mechanism of the reactions occurring in the thermal decomposition of sodium and potassium nitrites (presumably all alkali nitrites) may be represented as under :

I. The nitrites dissociate in the primary stage as

II. Nitrogen peroxide produced in (1) reacts with the oxide as in (2), and also with the undecomposed nitrite as in (3)

producing the nitrate.

III. The nitric oxide produced in (1) and (3) reacts with the unchanged nitrite to produce nitrogen as in (4)

The reactions (2), (3) and (4) go hand-in-hand.

IV. All the reactions occur in the molten phase though the possibility of the reactions (2), (3) and (4) occurring at the gas-liquid interface, in a closed system, is not ruled out.

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